

DELIVERABLE

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Short report on new hologram on protein-specific sorter D 3.3

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TABLE OF CONTENT

Table of Content	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. Test Protein Holograms	5
2. Holograms for the generalized OAM sorter	10
3. Holograms for the direct protein sorting	18
4. Conclusion	20
ANNEX 1: REFEREE	21
ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS	24
SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS	24
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	24

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to explain the design and the realization of specific holograms for the experiments of protein recognition. This design is based on the theoretical work done in the DE3.2.

The work is to be thought together with the coming deliverable on generalized e.m. sorter (DE3.4) as they are two alternatives for the same problem of protein recognition.

This is therefore propaedeutic for the protein recognition problem foreseen in del 3.3 that represents one of the final goals of the project.

The objective of this deliverable is to demonstrate how the hologram are designed with respect to their planned use in the Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) column and their actual feasibility as a real nanofabricated object. The feasibility of the hologram is not obvious since the Focused Ion Beam (FIB) nanofabrication can typically fabricate details down 50-100 nm depending on the working conditions. It is therefore very important to have a precise idea of the effective size of the objects based on the present version of the electrostatic sorter and the focal distances in the TITAN HOLO column.

In addition, we describe here another use of the hologram as a test for the sorter itself. In fact, we can produce holographic reproduction of the protein itself that are not sensitive to the damage and can be therefore used to test the sorter performances.

The current document is comprised of three main chapters, an Executive Summary and Conclusions. The first chapter introduces the ideas and realization of test holograms of proteins in both real and reciprocal space.

The second chapter describes the current design effort of the generalized OAM sorter based on the combination of the OAM sorter with the third, protein specific projector.

The third chapter discusses briefly the alternative idea to produce a protein specific sorter decoupled from an OAM sorter.

1. TEST PROTEIN HOLOGRAMS

1.1 Theory

Fig 1 Phase of the protein (top) and false colour image and phase of the FFT of the protein (2 different equalisations, bottom).

Looking at real proteins can be very complicated because of the radiation damage effects. So while we setup the OAM sorter we would like to be sure to be able to benchmark its performance in the ideal case.

In this section we will show the procedures to create a “virtual protein” inside the microscope.

Fig 1 shows the phase of the electron wave after passing through the protein. The phase varies between 0 and 1 rad so it is still a relatively weak phase object. Most importantly the amplitude change

due to the protein is quite small. Therefore the easiest way to simulate the protein is just to imprint the same phase as that of the protein.

This first approach is certainly very simple and effective but has a limitation. If the hologram is inserted in condenser aperture position it will be difficult to have the reconstructed image of the protein in focus in the specimen position. Depending on the electro optical configuration one would have the Fresnel or Fraunhofer image of the protein itself. That means that it is suitable to model other imaging condition beyond standard.

For a standard illumination it is probably also interesting to consider an hologram related to the Fourier Transform of the protein (see fig 1b,c) . Of course in this case the hologram cannot be a phase only object because the amplitude varies considerably with a large peak in the center of the hologram.

As an approximation we introduced a threshold in the amplitude of the FFT of the protein and used it as a mask for the phase hologram. Analytically the hologram can be written as

$$\varphi = [I(FT(\psi)) > th] \arg(FT(\psi))$$

Where the square bracket is 1 if I is greater than the threshold th and 0 otherwise. Examples of threshold are shown in fig 1 b,c.

The resulting hologram is shown in fig 2a,b.

Notice that we did not apply an amplitude so most of the hologram diffraction will just go in the center.

Fig 2 SEM images of the direct and Fourier holograms of the protein.

1.2 Experimental realization and analysis

Fig 3 TEM image and diffraction of the direct and Fourier hologram.

Fig 4. Fresnel out of focus images of the protein hologram in direct (left, center) and FT space (right).

Fig 3 shows the image and the diffraction from the holograms that has been fabricated by FIB on a SiN membrane . The SiN was coated by gold that was removed only in the hologram region.

Clearly all virtual proteins have a 7-fold symmetry that is the essential fact in order to test the OAM sorter ability to sort symmetries. Notice in particular that the first hologram is very similar to the protein image in fig 1 and the that the diffraction of the FT hologram is indeed very similar to the original molecule except for the central intensity peak . An image in out of focus for both holograms is also shown in fig 4 resembling typical out of focus images of real proteins.

2. HOLOGRAMS FOR THE GENERALIZED OAM SORTER

2.1 ray tracing

Fig 5 Ray tracing in two configurations allowing for sorters in OBJ, SAD1 , SAD2 (located before and after the XL lens of the TITAN HOLO microscope) apertures (see Del 2.1) but produce a different size of the diffraction of sorter2 in the sorter3 position.

Fig 5 shows two possible electro-optics configurations with generalized sorter. In these configurations the electrostatic sorters are placed as usual in OBJ and SAD1, while the additional hologram must be placed in SAD2. For further details about these apertures see Del 3.1.

Fig 6 schematic of the configuration with 3 sorter for generalizing OAM sorter in order to recognize a protein.

The actual scheme of the optics is shown in fig 6 showing the need of a third phase element S3 coupled with a cylindrical lens.

Two alternate rays are highlighted in dark and light red. They correspond to parallel and convergent beam on the specimen plane. So the alternate series of crossovers shown the alternate image (dark red) and diffraction (light red) planes.

This is just one of the possible configurations. The most important point to establish here is the focal that can be changed with continuity. The second configuration produces a focal of about 8cm that is exactly the distance between the XL lens and the SAD2. This is not in general the maximum focal we can obtain between the two planes since we could imagine to put a crossover just in front of the XL. But this is extremely challenging since that would mean that image and diffraction planes should be incredibly close. For reasonable lens conditions the focal cannot exceed 8 cm.

Therefore we assume from now on that $f = 8\text{cm}$.

2.2 Calculating the eigen- protein

The theoretical scheme is that reproduced in del 3.2. We imagine our task is to distinguish between the two protein here below . They are very similar but distinguished by the different symmetry (6 and 7fold).

Fig 7 phase of the two proteins to be discriminated.

We refer here to deliverable 3.2 and even better in the paper arXiv:2001.08918. According to the recipe, for the optimal discrimination a projector must be calculated and used based not on the single protein but on a combination of the two that permits to highlight the orthogonal component between the two proteins.

The combination of the two proteins can be formally calculated as in the paper above leading to two eigen-proteins that are shown in fig 8.

Fig 8 Intensity and phase of the eigen-proteins obtained as optimal combination of the initial protein in fig 7.

As established in our paper the projector on this eigenstate made by phase flattening. The S3 phase element is therefore characterized by a phase that is just the phase of the eigen-proteins in the OAM representation but changed in sign. Of course the use of holograms is not optimal by itself as it implies the loss of about 50% of the electrons incident on the sample so this can be only considered as a proof of principle while electro magnetic counterpart is surely more suitable. However, as we will see the dimensions of the feature could be demanding for an electrostatic phase element.

2.3 Calculating the hologram

We started from fig 8b that transformed in the Fourier Log polar coordinates of S3 looks like fig 7. This is our initial guess for the projector on the negative eigenstate.

Fig 9 FT of log polar transformation of fig 8b. This can be considered the ideal projector on this state and the ideal phase plate for optimal discrimination.

The Fourier Log polar transformation has been obtained using ideal coordinate transformation but simulations shows that a realistic sorter would only add a phase gradient corresponding to tilt and shift that are separately accounted for.

The image of fig 9 would be already good but we think we can improve it by removing completely the tilt effect again since this effect can be better introduced by tilt and shift coils. This should allow for less steep phase changes and potentially less challenges in fabrication and alignment,

For this we did the following mathematical operation: 1) unwrap the phase (fig 8a) and fit and remove a linear gradient (fig 8b). This permits to remove the linear component. 2) rewrap the phase

Fig 10 Procedure of removal of the linear gradient.

In fig 11 we cut the central area and rewrapped it in the $-\pi$ $+\pi$ range. The horizontal axis corresponds to OAM , the vertical to log-radial-momentum.

Fig 11 new phase plate – projector obtained after linear gradient removal and zoom

For definiteness we will assume that the sorter 2 periodicity d is $10\ \mu\text{m}$ that is the current value. Probably a reduction by a factor 2 is possible and would make this work even easier.

The sorter 2 diffraction, namely the separation between different OAM channels (and therefore the pixel size in the image above) has to be

$$t = \frac{\lambda f}{d}$$

If the focal is 8 cm and $d=10\ \mu\text{m}$ $t=160\ \text{nm}$.

Alternatively, we can resample the image above by a factor 2 and use a pixel of 80 nm. When limited to an OAM range $[-64\ 64]$ this corresponds to a full hologram side of $20\ \mu\text{m}$. Both these specs are within the standard of the fabrication. The result is shown in fig 11b

2.4 Adding cylindrical lens term

At this point one coordinate has to be focused in a point while the other must image in itself.

We must therefore combine the hologram and the lens to obtain a directional lens effect.

This can be accomplished by different approaches.

We chose to fix the lens focal to 8 cm and introduce a cylindrical lens in the OAM dispersion direction giving a $-8\ \text{cm}$ focal effect that compensates for the lens completely.

Alternatively we could have used a quadrupolar correction and vary the lens excitation. This can be optimal to reduce the phase gradient in the hologram but results in a more complicated alignment.

The cylindrical lens effect we need to imprint has $f=-8$ cm.

The phase is therefore

$$\varphi = a r^2$$

With $a = \frac{\pi}{\lambda f} w^2$ where r is normalized to 1 and w is the hologram width. We find $a=2500$.

Fig 12 Same as fig 11 but with addition of the necessary cylindrical lens effect.

2.5 Hologram realisation

Fig 13 shows the actually fabricated membrane of SiN of the pattern with and without the cylindrical lens component. Please compare with fig 11 and fig 12.

The image is taken with SEM and shows that in the case without the cylindrical component the pattern is correctly reproduced. In the case of the second pattern we find that there are problems in the peripheral part of the pattern where the lens term becomes too large. However the effect of this higher frequency region is typically less important.

Fig 13 SEM image of the experimental hologram of the SORTER3 without (left) and with (right) the lensing term.

3. HOLOGRAMS FOR THE DIRECT PROTEIN SORTING

We show here mainly for completeness the two holograms for direct sorting of proteins. This contains no optimization and is not invariant for protein rotation but it is a good example of protein recognition in an abstract case.

These holograms are therefore based on del 3.1. and the proteins chosen are those in fig 7.

This is a route that hasn't been followed in the rest of the project but has a potential interest as an example of generalized sorter.

Fig 14 Theoretical hologram for protein sorting according to del 3.1.

Fig 15 Experimental realisation of the two phase elements with SiN membranes.

4. CONCLUSION

To conclude we have demonstrated three families of holograms potentially useful for the realization of protein specific sorter. A first family is just a reproduction of the protein in both direct and reciprocal space. The second is the hologram to be inserted as third element in a generalized OAM sorter. The third is a protein specific sorter made of two phase elements.

The results show a successful control of the electron beam wave in all cases. However, the most interesting case is that of the generalized OAM sorter. We have shown calculations that are useful also for the fully electrostatic case and we have shown that we can achieve this resolution with a phase hologram. The realization of the fully electrostatic device seems to be more controversial since the required resolution is of the order of few hundred nm. With an improvement of the electrostatic elements details down to 500 nm and a tuning of the electrostatic sorter² periodicity to 5 μm one could probably match the optimal conditions with the future sorter 3 programmable phase plate but it is important to see that there is a backup in SiN based holograms.

ANNEX 1: REFEREE

A1.1 Referee 1

The work is concise and well written. The topic is very interesting and the realization of the full electronic configuration is very ambitious. I hope this will work but I have some questions.

- 1) The phase of the S3 element seems to be quite complicated , are you sure we can generate it by an electrostatic element?
- 2) There seems to be serious problem in centering the hologram S3, what solution can you foresee for the exact alignment. How sensible is the final result to this?
- 3) What is the interest of the part 3 if this sorting system is working only for one exact protein orientation?
- 4) How do you plan to immobilize the protein in real experiments. How much will it matter for protein identification.

Dear referee. Thank you for your comment. I know we are getting to the difficult and ambiguous part of the project and it is necessary to clarify all aspects before going on.

- 1) Most of the apparent difficulty appears as an effect of wrapping of the phase. The unwrapped phase appears indeed quite smooth so that it should be possible to approximate it locally with an harmonic phase function generated by sparse electrodes.
There is an additional point that is worth pointing out. Most of the information is contained in the component $m=0$. This result has been highlighted in the context of the paper (arXiv:2001.08918). This is due to mainly to the fact that the intensity of this channel is orders of magnitude higher than any other. This information is useful to answer also about point two.*
- 2) In the real device it will be necessary to highlight the part of the hologram corresponding to $m=0$ as this will be the most visible feature of virtually any protein's OAM spectrum. This will certainly facilitate the alignment. Of course a reference spectrum with vacuum should further help. Finally we hope that the use of virtual proteins can be of use exactly in this case.*
- 3) The interest is mainly outside the project as a demonstration of the possibility of mode sorting in electron optics. The use of two holograms makes it useless for proteins but of general interest as outcome of the project.*
- 4) This question is less related to this deliverable and more to the real experiment realization. Our hope is that we can use STEM imaging to position the probe on the protein with a minimal damage before actually proceed to the identification. We don't have still a measure of how critical will the alignment be but this will be clarified with further simulation. A realistic number for the generalized sorter here seems to be 1 nm. This is another good reason why experiments with "virtual proteins" will be very important as a demonstration of principle.*

A1.2 Referee 2

Thank you for your work . Let me ask you a comment and express my doubts.

- 1) Can you discuss about the effect of inelastically scattered electrons from the virtual protein hologram as well as the third hologram (in SAD2) and especially their joint effects?
- 2) Protein is a weak or pure phase object. Even you have design a phase hologram. However, what would be the amplitude effect of 50 nm SiN in your calculation?
- 3) Have you considered electron beam induce charging effect of SiN? especially in C2 plane? or in sample plane when you are using a focused probe (STEM)?
- 4) what is the real size of the protein? can you discuss about your convergence angle or in general probe size to be able to observe the symmetry details of the virtual protein?
- 5) Is it correct that with the third Sorter hologram in SAD 2 you can only answer if this is the right protein or not? Also, is it correct that you may distinguished the symmetry of an unknown protein only using the programmable phase plate as Sorter 3?

Dear referee thanks for your questions.

- 1) In our experience the inelastically scattering of hologram located in the condenser aperture are negligible. This is particularly true when the probe is indeed exactly the Fourier transform of the hologram. The inelastic scattering is indeed diffuse and located at angle ranges that are slightly different from those typical of the hologram scattering. So far we haven't actually experienced any clear feature of inelastic scattering in experiments even using energy filtered diffraction. To large extent this can be considered a background. The situation with S3 could be more complicated because it acts on a different angular range due to the magnification effect. It could be a real disturbance because in the count of the electron in diffraction a background is really detrimental of the protein testing algorithm. For a real experiment we can use GIF to energy filter the result. But As said the holographic S3 option is only to be used as a second possibility.*
- 2) The amplitude effect is not completely negligible both for real and simulated protein. The real protein have a standard deviation difference of phase of 0.1rad , and an amplitude standard deviation of 7% (intensity change 14%). This corresponds in terms of hologram to thickness difference of 1nm and an amplitude difference of 1%. In reality the phase of the hologram has been largely amplified but still the amplitude modulation are in the average below 10%.*
- 3) Electron beam charging on SiN can be a serious problem. Mitigation measures include the coverage with evaporated gold on both sides but if the aperture is appropriately shaped the main effect of the charging is accounted for as lensing. Indeed the experimental hologram diffraction in fig 3 reproduce reasonably our expectation for the wavefunction.*

- 4) *The real size of the protein is roughly 10 nm. With an appropriate choice of the convergence angle we can fit the hologram diffraction to the realistic size. More precisely we need feature of the order of $s=1 \mu\text{m}$ to be Fourier transformed into 10 nm.*

$$d = \frac{f\lambda}{s}$$
$$f \approx 0.01 \text{ m}$$

If the aperture is $A=20 \mu\text{m}$ we find

$$\alpha = \frac{A}{f} \approx 1 \text{ mrad}$$

- 5) *More correctly we can optimally distinguish between protein A and B. Of course it is anyway a measurement in a custom basis there is much more than an A or B answer. Through unitary transformation no information is lost. We can distinguish the symmetry of the protein even without s_3 and S_3 should not alter this capacity. However the blind ability to recognize proteins is more demanding than protein recognition in terms of dose.*

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Multi Modal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL